

ISic0448

I.Sicily inscription 0448

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---][][---]

2. [---][me]moria a[---]

3. [---Ana]stasi[o]

4. [---] co(n)[s(ulibus)]

Apparatus

Text and reconstructions from CIL

The first letter should be 'L' or 'E', the second either 'C' or 'O'

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491676

EDCS 21900510

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7169 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650769>)

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